

Ketenes as privileged synthons in the syntheses of heterocyclic compounds part 2: Five-membered heterocycles

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Abstract

Ketenes are mostly used as the remarkable and common starting materials for structurally diverse five-membered and fused five-membered compounds, such as lactones, furans, benzofurans, dioxolane derivatives, pyrroles, succinimide, indoles, oxindoles, isoindoles, thiophenes, oxazoles, benzoxazoles, isoxazolols, oxathiolane derivatives, thiazoles, and thiadiazoles.

Keyword

Furans, Indoles, Isoindoles, Isoxazolols, Ketene, Oxazoles, Oxindoles, Pyrroles, Thiazoles, thiadiazoles Thiophenes